

MALIMATH COMMITTEE & POLICE REFORMS - A COMIC GUIDE

An Essential Guide to Justice System Reforms

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Who was Malimath, sir?

Justice V.S. Malimath, former Chief Justice of Karnataka and Kerala High Courts. A very respected judge with deep knowledge of criminal law.

5. About the Malimath

Their mission was very simple — to make justice faster, fairer & people-friendly for all citizens.

MISSION:

- FASTER JUSTICE
- FAIRER JUSTICE
- PEOPLE-FRIENDLY SYSTEM

6. The team's Mission

What did they study exactly?

Everything! From how police investigate, to how courts handle cases, and even how victims and witnesses are treated.

7. Studying the System

They wanted to understand real-life problems faced by common people.

Oo..wow

8. Public Involvement:
The committee didn't just sit in offices. They traveled, met police officials, judges, lawyers, NGOs, and the public..etc.

So justice was hard to get for common people!

They found ,the system had serious issues — delays, corruption, lack of staff, and outdated methods.

9 . What They Found ?

Their vision was “Justice for all — without fear or delay.”

10.The Committee’s Vision:
The committee wanted a modern justice system — fair to both victims and accused.

Did they talk about using technology?

Absolutely! They wanted more use of DNA testing, fingerprints, CCTV & forensics to make evidence stronger.

13. Use of Science

I heard the term "plea bargaining." What is that?

It means if someone admits guilt in a small case, the punishment can be lighter — saving time and money for the courts.

14. Plea Bargaining

Did they suggest any new systems?

Yes, like digital record keeping, forensic labs, women's help desks, and CCTV monitoring in police stations.

So did the government follow all their suggestions

Yes — cybercrime cells and CCTV were added. But many important ideas, like full witness protection, are still not done.

Some states made progress, but others didn't.
Political pressure, lack of funds, and slow decision-making are still big barriers.

CHALLENGES REMAIN

- POLITICAL PRESSURE
- LACK OF FUNDS
- SLOW DECISION-MAKING

Even today, the Malimath Report is like a guidebook for reforms.

So it's still useful!

Sir, did other countries also make such committees?

Very good question. Yes, many countries reformed their justice systems — like UK, USA, & Canada focusing on victims' rights and speedy trials.

Sir, what about emotional support for victims?

The committee suggested setting up Victim Support Cells to provide counseling & help victims recover mentally and socially.

22. Victim Support Services
Justice is not only about punishment, it's also about healing.

Many people have fear from the police. Did the committee talk about that?

Yes, they said the police must act as “protectors,” not the “controllers.” Public trust should be their main goal.

25. Police-Public Relationship
A friendly & trained police force ensures public confidence in law.

So sir, do you think full reforms will happen one day?

I believe that If our generation demands transparency & fairness, change will surely come.

26. Hope for the Future
The journey of reform is long — but every step counts toward justice for all.

**Thank you,
sir! I really
understand
now.**

**I'm glad.
Always
remember
— Justice
delayed is
justice
denied.**

**The Malimath Committee
didn't just suggest changes
— it lit the path toward a
fair and strong democracy.**

MALIMATH COMMITTEE & POLICE REFORMS

A COMIC LEARNING JOURNEY

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